

Bank Account Ownership and Market Access of Female Smallholder Farmers in Ogun State

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ABSTRACT

Agriculture being a major part of many African economies is very imperative in providing food, industrial raw materials, jobs, as well as trade opportunities. Smallholder farmers, particularly female, are crucial to this sector as their positive impact greatly enhances food security and rural development. This study evaluated the influence of bank account ownership on the market access of female smallholder farmers in Ogun State. The study employed a descriptive quantitative research design. Using a multi-stage sampling procedure 295 respondents were randomly selected from the 1,228 female smallholder farmers belonging to the female farmer organizations spread across eight LGAs of Ogun State. Data were gathered using a structured questionnaire and were analysed using descriptive statistics, and regression analysis. Findings revealed that bank account ownership significantly enhanced market access among female smallholder farmers. The study concluded that financial inclusion plays a crucial role in enhancing the productivity and economic well-being of female smallholder farmers in Ogun State. It therefore recommended that financial institutions should promote savings schemes tailored to the needs of female smallholder farmers.

Keywords: Agriculture, Bank Account Ownership, Female Smallholder Farmers, Financial Inclusion, Financial Institutions

Word Count: 172

Introduction

Nigeria, as the most populous country on the continent, heavily relies on its agricultural sector for food security, employment, and income generation. As much as 70% of the Nigerian population is directly or indirectly involved in agriculture. Agriculture being a major part of many African economies is very imperative in providing food, industrial raw materials, jobs, as well as trade opportunities. Most of the African population lives in rural areas, and their lives are heavily dependent on agriculture (Mapanje, Karuaihe, Macheche, & Amis, 2023). In Nigeria's economy, Agriculture plays a significant role in helping millions of livelihoods and providing major opportunities for economic growth. Smallholder farmers, particularly female, are crucial to this sector as their positive impact greatly enhances food security and rural development (Munonye, Matthew, Olaolu, et al 2023). However, female smallholder farmers in Ogun State, like their peers throughout the country, face continuous obstacles that limit their productivity and economic enablement.

The challenges at the intersection of gender and financial exclusion severely restrict the potential of these female smallholder farmers. Financial inclusion is more than an economic tool; it is a major key factor of change (Saha & Qin, 2023). In Ogun State, where agriculture is both a traditional practice and a critical part of the economy, female smallholder farmers face especially challenging challenges. Many of these women remain trapped in a cycle of low productivity due to limited access to financial services designed for their specific needs, hindering their ability to seize agricultural opportunities that their male counterparts more easily access (Bankole 2024). This scenario represents not only an economic injustice but also a major lost opportunity to improve food security and promote rural development.

Female smallholder farmers play a significant role in Nigerian agriculture, contributing substantially to the nation's food production and economic stability (Civil Resource Development and Documentation Centre, 2022). The importance of addressing the needs and challenges faced by female smallholder farmers in Nigeria is evident. A vital aspect of their empowerment and socio-economic development lies in ensuring their access to financial resources, also known as financial inclusion (Adegbite & Machethe, 2020). Financial inclusion encompasses not only the availability of financial services but also the capacity of individuals to use these services effectively.

Gender disparities in land ownership, control over resources, and decision-making in agriculture persist, which disproportionately affect female smallholder farmers. These disparities contribute to their vulnerability and limit their capacity to make long-term investments and sustainable agricultural decisions (Runde & Nealer, 2015). The lack of access to credit, modern agricultural inputs, and technology hampers the agricultural productivity of female smallholder farmers. This not only restrains their income generation but also perpetuates food insecurity and poverty in the region (Mathan, & Sunderaraj, 2024). In gaining financial inclusion and improving their incomes, sociocultural norms and traditions, including limited mobility, restricted participation in community activities, and restricted access to extension services, have created additional hurdles for female smallholder farmers.

This study aims to encourage female smallholder farmers' financial inclusion in order to give these farmers better access to vital financial services including savings accounts, credit, and risk management instruments. More economic opportunities, a decrease in poverty, and better living conditions for female smallholder farmers and their communities are all results of this inclusion. Specifically, the study aim is to:

- i. evaluate the influence of bank account ownership on the market access of female smallholder farmers in Ogun State.

Literature Review

Financial Inclusion: Bridging the Divide

The accessibility and utilization of financial inclusion solutions have emerged as pivotal determinants of agricultural productivity and income among women farmers, especially in the agrarian landscapes of Ogun State, Nigeria, where smallholder farming is a cornerstone of

livelihoods (The Guardian, 2023). The harmonization of marginalized groups, particularly female smallholder farmers, holds an outstanding relevance in the hunt for sustainable food production and the enhancement of the economic well-being of communities (United Nations, 2023). The evolution of financial mechanisms, spanning from conventional banking services to innovative mobile payment platforms and community-based savings groups, has brought to the fore a tapestry of possibilities and challenges (Kalaitzakis, 2020). These financial inclusion solutions focus on empowering female smallholder farmers by providing them with access to credit, savings, insurance, and digital payment systems, fostering economic independence and resilience in the face of agricultural risks.

On the other hand, the dynamics of financial inclusion among female smallholder farmers in Ogun State are a complex narrative. Deep-rooted sociocultural norms, limited access to extension services, and gender-related constraints create formidable barriers to full involvement of women in these financial systems (Adegbite & Adeoye, 2018). This multifaceted landscape necessitates an extensive exploration of scholarly insights and empirical evidence to unravel the intricate web of factors influencing both financial inclusion adoption and its consequent impacts on agricultural productivity and income among female smallholder farmers (Ifediora, et al 2022).

Financial inclusion (FI) is described as the access to and use of a broad range of formal financial services and products at affordable cost by all population groups, while ensuring that those who are marginalized financially are included (CGAP 2015). Financial inclusion is clearly outlined as the systematic effort to encourage the availability of financial products and services that are affordable, punctual, and adequate, ensuring their extensive utilization across all societal strata. This is executed through the application of customized and creative strategies, including initiatives aimed at enhancing financial literacy and education.

Financial inclusion, commonly recognized as a pivotal catalyst for economic development, is grounded in the core principle of guaranteeing that both individuals and businesses have the means to access and efficiently utilize financial services (UNSGSA). 2023. The core of financial inclusion is not limited to mere access; it extends to fostering active participation and empowerment, especially among marginalized populations. Financial inclusion extends its reach to those on the fringes of the formal financial sector, striving to embrace the marginalized, among whom lie the primary subjects: female smallholder farmers.

Smallholder Farmers

The Smallholder farmers, despite their marginalization, play a very essential and crucial role in the agricultural productivity of the country, which constitutes 80% of all farmers, and produce over 90% of the overall national agricultural production, and are mainly the primary driver of activities in the agricultural sector (Mgbenka & Mbah, 2016). In the agricultural landscapes of Ogun State, Nigeria, smallholder farmers form the bedrock of food production. These individuals, predominantly women, engage in subsistence and small-scale farming, contributing significantly to local food security and rural economies. These women, often overlooked in the broader agricultural landscape, play an indispensable role in food production, rural development, and the sustainability of the agricultural sector, and they are characterized by limited land holdings,

resource constraints, and a dedication to subsistence farming. Providing support for the smallholder farmers can therefore assist in enhancing food security in the country. A critical strategy should be in place for smallholder farmers for their development and securing the present and future livelihood of the country's population. Given the need for Nigeria to diversify its economy to agriculture and the crucial role of rural smallholder farmers, there is a need to intensify efforts to ensure FI makes significant impacts in agriculture, rural livelihood, and economic growth (Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development, 2017)

The Nexus of Financial Inclusion and Agricultural Productivity

Agricultural productivity encompasses the efficiency, yield, and economic output of agricultural activities, productivity indicators include crop yield, income generated, the utilization of sustainable agricultural practices, and the capacity to adapt to environmental challenges, which acts as the bridge between financial inclusion solutions and the livelihoods of female smallholder farmers (Onogwu, Audu & Igbodor, 2021). Procurement of quality inputs, and management of risk can find a good expression when there is access to credit, savings, and insurance services can bolster farmers' capacity to invest in modern agricultural practices, the adoption of financial inclusion solutions offers the promise of improved agricultural productivity, for female smallholder farmers in Ogun State.

The effects of financial inclusion on agriculture have been drawn from the role finance plays in affecting poverty and inequality. Availability of finance has brought about an increase in agricultural productivity and higher incomes for the farmer. As a result of this, the hunger of the poor is reduced, and they can escape poverty traps and withstand periodic shocks (Anthony-Orji, et al 2024). Finance can foster agricultural productivity for a smallholder farmer, financial inclusion can assist in mitigating a lot of the challenges faced by the farmers, as financial products are available in the form of credit or even savings products.

The Role of Fintech in Promoting Financial Inclusion

Fintech solutions have been demonstrated as powerful tools in addressing the barriers faced by female smallholder farmers, offering innovative approaches to enhance their financial inclusion and empowerment (Arner, Buckley & Zetsche, 2020). Mobile banking, digital payments, and online lending platforms are among the fintech services that have revolutionized the financial landscape for these farmers. Women in Nigeria are less likely to have access to formal financial services than men, with only 34% of women having a bank account compared to 44% of men (Landry & Usman, 2021). Fintech can help bridge this gap by providing digital financial services that are accessible through mobile phones, even in remote areas. This can help women smallholder farmers save money, transfer funds, and access other financial services that were previously unavailable to them. Fintech solutions, such as mobile banking, have revolutionized the way farmers manage their finances which has set free from traditional banking institutions which often have stringent requirements, making it difficult for these farmers to save, borrow, and conduct transactions, delivering the female smallholder farmers from one crucial challenge of limited access to formal financial services. Through mobile banking platforms, farmers can access their

accounts, make deposits, and transfer funds conveniently and securely, without the need for a physical bank branch.

Digital payment systems are another fintech innovation that has positively impacted female smallholder farmers. These systems allow farmers to receive payments for their produce directly into their accounts, eliminating the need for physical cash transactions. This not only enhances the security of their earnings but also provides a record of their financial activities, facilitating access to credit and other financial services. Online lending platforms have also emerged as a valuable resource for female smallholder farmers. These platforms connect farmers directly with lenders, eliminating intermediaries and reducing the complexities associated with obtaining loans. Fintech enables farmers to access credit more efficiently, promoting investment in their agricultural activities and enabling them to expand their operations by digitizing the lending process. It has been widely recognized as a key driver of financial inclusion, particularly in developing countries.

Fintech interventions bridge the gap between traditional financial services and the underserved population. By leveraging technology and innovative solutions, fintech companies create financial products and services tailored to the specific needs of female smallholder farmers. These solutions are designed to be accessible, affordable, and user-friendly, ensuring that farmers can easily navigate and benefit from the digital financial ecosystem. Through these fintech interventions, female smallholder farmers can experience increased financial inclusion and empowerment. The ability to save, borrow, and conduct transactions more efficiently enhances their economic resilience and improves their overall well-being. By overcoming the barriers that have traditionally hindered their access to financial services, fintech empowers these farmers to take control of their financial lives and participate more actively in economic activities.

Theoretical Review

This study anchored on Theories of Financial Inclusion Delivery (Public-Private Partnership (PPP). Regarding the organizations in charge of providing the general public with official financial services, different points of view exist. Some call for government involvement in the provision of these services (Ramadhan & Robin, 2024; Basnayake, et al, 2024). Others, on the other hand, assert that businesses in the private sector, such as banks and financial technology firms, can provide these services to the general public more successfully (Ghosh & Vinod,2017; Basnayake, et al, 2024) In addition, some viewpoints contend that a cooperative effort between the public and private sectors may be the best strategy for providing formal financial services (Nkechika,2023; Pearce, 2011).

According to the Theories of financial inclusion delivery (Public-Private Partnership (PPP) formal financial services can be efficiently provided to the general public through cooperation between private sector companies, such as banks and financial technology corporations, and government bodies. According to this notion, combining the advantages of both industries can result in a financial inclusion plan that is more effective and all-encompassing.

Empirical Review

Fowowe, (2020) asserted that financial inclusion, irrespective of how it is measured, has exerted positive and statistically significant effects on agricultural productivity in Nigeria. It therefore emphasizes the need to further strengthen the financial inclusion efforts in the country. The study also inferred that it would be beneficial if policy-makers put in place policies favourable to women to participate in agriculture. This is because, according to findings, female-headed households are associated with lower agricultural productivity. This brings to light the patriarchal nature of agricultural production in Nigeria. However, an increasing number of research have shown that poverty falls faster for female-headed households in Africa, hence, policies that favour financial inclusion for women will be very helpful (Outreach International, 2023). Part of the findings also stated that variables measuring account ownership and savings are consistently associated with significant positive effects on agricultural productivity, unlike the variable measuring borrowing. Generally speaking, borrowing can be said to reflect access to credit, which is also considered as an indicator of financial inclusion, however, if the cost and terms of borrowing are heavy and stringent, it may erode the benefit that should be derived from such borrowing, hence, it may not result in improved agricultural productivity.

Account ownership with Non-Bank Financial Institutions (NBFIs), such as Village Savings and Loan Associations (VSLAs), displayed the narrowest gender gap among the financial inclusion metrics, indicating a more balanced representation between male and female smallholder horticultural farmers in this particular financial sector (Soekarnia, et al, 2024). The study's findings emphasize the need for targeted efforts to enhance financial inclusion among female smallholder farmers in the horticultural sector. It was therefore suggested that since the women smallholders find it easier to own accounts at Non-Bank Financial Institutions such as Village Savings and Loan Associations (VSLAs), there is a need to facilitate the linkage of NBFIs such as the Village Savings and Loan Associations (VSLAs) to Bank Financial Institutions (BFIs) for better financial inclusion impacts. It was further established that female farmers participating in Village Savings and Loans Associations (VSLAs) are better positioned to pursue alternative income-generating activities and make critical investments in their agricultural operations. According to Solidaridad Network, (2024) regular participation in these savings groups allows rural women in Nigeria to access pooled credit that can be invested in business improvements, farm enhancements, and children's education, thereby creating pathways to sustainable livelihoods beyond subsistence farming. In the same vein Adegbite (2021) observed that significant gender and geographical variations exist in the levels of financial inclusion of rural smallholder farmers. Also, not all rural smallholders who have access to finance in a regulated system are financially adequate. That means having formal access to finance is not significantly the same as having financial inclusion. Therefore, if the policy goal is to optimize the financial inclusion of rural smallholder farmers, then it is important that policy interventions be made to address the gaps between formal access and the financial adequacy of rural smallholders in a regulated financial system. While the National Financial Inclusion strategy in Nigeria identified gender and regional gaps, among others, for policy attention, there are still no differentiated targets for smallholder farmers by gender or region. If the policy goal is aimed at closing the FI gender disparity, then there is a need to implement gender-differentiated policy interventions with greater emphasis on enhancing the financial inclusion of rural women smallholder farmers (Adegbite, 2021). There should be increased focus on enhancing the adequacy

of rural women smallholder farmers in FI indicators, such as formal access to finance, financial literacy, control over finance, and financial resilience. Moreover, there is a need to increase gender awareness on the part of males who play supportive roles in female financial inclusion and control over finance.

Ghosh and Vinod (2017) as well as Damane and Ho (2024) have emphasized the empowerment of female smallholder farmers through financial inclusion. Financial inclusion can lead to increased economic independence, decision-making power, and enhanced social status for women in rural areas. These studies stress the transformative potential of financial inclusion for female farmers.

Chinoda and Kapingura (2024) opined that the relationship between access to credit and income growth among female smallholder farmers has been a recurring theme. This is particularly important for female farmers who often face constraints in accessing financial resources. In the context of the growing prevalence of digital financial inclusion solutions, the significance of technology in enhancing access to financial services for female smallholder farmers has been emphasized. Mobile money platforms and USSD-based services have played a pivotal role in broadening financial inclusion.

Vivian and Peter (2023) affirmed that drawing on the use of technology to improve financial inclusion and the associated benefits, it has been concluded that women agripreneurs in Southern Nigeria who have access to digital financial products achieve higher incomes and savings compared to those without such access. In the field of financial inclusion, especially when considering gender disparities, women frequently encounter a range of barriers that restrict their economic engagement in comparison to men (World Bank, 2017; Udensi & Akintunde, 2024). Previous empirical research has consistently demonstrated the substantial impact of gender on formal financial access (Reynolds, et al 2017; Ugwuja & Anusie, 2024). In their study, digital financial services and their relationship with gender, identifying factors linked to awareness, adoption, and utilization. Reynolds et al (2017) explored the factors influencing financial inclusion in Central and West Africa, underlining the importance of gender within the context of financial inclusion.

According to Setiani, Pratiwi and Komara (2024) there is a positive relationship between formal financial access, financial literacy, and income generation. Having access to formal financial services and possessing financial literacy significantly enhances the capacity to generate income through mechanisms such as saving, credit acquisition, asset accumulation, and risk management. This empowerment leads to the development of entrepreneurial skills and a greater exploration of economic opportunities.

Methodology

The study employed a descriptive quantitative research design. The population of this study comprised 1,228 female smallholder farmers belonging to the female farmer organizations spread across eight LGAs of Ogun State. A multi-stage sampling procedure which includes purposive sampling, cluster sampling and random sampling techniques, was adopted. Using Krejcie & Morgan (1970), 295 respondents were randomly selected. Data were gathered using a structured questionnaire consisting of both open-ended and closed-ended questions for the collection of

quantitative data through primary sources. Data were analysed through descriptive statistics, and regression analysis.

Presentation of Data

Demographic Analysis of Respondents

There are two hundred and ninety-five (295) distributed questionnaires, and all were retrieved by the researcher. All of the questionnaires were correctly filled and used for the analysis, which represents a 100 per cent response rate as presented in Table 1

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Female Smallholder Farmers in the study

s/n	Variables	Labels	Frequency	Percentage
1	Gender	Male	-	-
		Female	295	100.0
2	Age	20-25 years	17	5.8
		30-35 years	76	25.8
		40-45 years	70	23.7
		46 years and above	132	44.7
3	Years of work experience	Below 10 years	65	22.0
		10-20 years	131	44.4
		Above 20 years	99	33.6
4	Highest level of education	First Leaving Certificate	202	68.5
		OND/NCE	44	14.9
		Professional qualification	1	0.3
		Degree	47	15.9
		Masters	1	0.3
5	Marital status	Single	12	4.1
		Married	277	93.9
		Divorced	1	0.3
		Separated	5	1.7
6	Number of dependents	No dependent	1	0.3

		1-5 dependents	197	66.8
		6-10 dependents	92	31.2
		11-15 dependents	4	1.4
		Above 15 dependents	1	0.3
7	Years of farming experience	Less than 5 years	18	6.1
		5-10 years	101	34.2
		11-20 years	96	32.5
		More than 20 years	80	27.1

Source: Fieldwork (2025)

Table 1 shows the demographic characteristics of female smallholder farmers in the study. The age distribution showed that the majority of female farmers (44.7%) are aged 46 and above, followed by 30-35 years (25.8%), while younger farmers (20-25 years) are the minority at 5.8%. This indicated that most female farmers in the study are middle-aged or older, suggesting a possible trend of aging in the farming population. Additionally, the majority have significant work experience, with 44.4% having worked for 10-20 years, indicating that these women are seasoned farmers with extensive knowledge of farming practices.

In terms of education, the majority (68.5%) have only a First Leaving Certificate, which is the most basic level of education. A small proportion (15.9%) had a degree, while less than 1% hold a professional qualification or a master's degree. This showed a disparity in education levels among the farmers, which could affect their ability to adopt new technologies or farming practices. Furthermore, a significant majority of the women (93.9%) are married, which indicates that family support systems are an important factor in their ability to engage in farming activities.

Regarding dependents and farming experience, most farmers (66.8%) have between 1-5 dependents, with a smaller proportion (31.2%) having 6-10 dependents. This indicated a substantial family responsibility for many farmers, potentially influencing their labour capacity and financial needs. When it comes to farming experience, a considerable number of farmers (34.2%) have been farming for 5-10 years, and nearly as many (32.5%) have 11-20 years of experience. Those farming for more than 20 years represented 27.1%, while the least experienced (less than 5 years) made up only 6.1%. This showed that the majority have substantial farming experience.

Presentation of Research Question

Research Question: What is the influence of bank account ownership on the investment in quality input for female smallholder farmers?

Table 2: Influence of bank account ownership on market access among female smallholder farmers

s/n	Bank account ownership	SD	D	U	A	SA	\bar{x}	S.D.
1	A bank account improves access to agricultural markets.	1 0.3%	2 0.7%	1 0.3%	151 51.2%	140 47.5%	4.45	0.580
2	It streamlines transactions with buyers.	1 0.3%	1 0.3%	2 0.7%	172 58.3%	119 40.3%	4.38	0.558
3	It boosts my farm's market reputation.	3 1.0%	2 0.7%	3 1.0%	185 62.7%	102 34.6%	4.29	0.625
4	It helps secure better product prices.	1 0.3%	8 2.7%	21 7.1%	184 62.4%	81 27.5%	4.14	0.683
5	It aids in accessing market insights.	2 0.7%	7 2.4%	20 6.8%	179 60.7%	87 29.5%	4.16	0.704
6	It offers financial transaction flexibility.	1 0.3%	4 1.4%	11 3.7%	162 54.9%	117 39.7%	4.32	0.645
7	It provides easier access to formal finance.	1 0.3%	4 1.4%	12 4.1%	190 64.4%	88 29.8%	4.22	0.614
8.	It enables safer electronic payments.	-	4 1.4%	4 1.4%	147 49.8%	140 47.5%	4.43	0.596
9	It strengthens relationships with market players.	2 0.7%	1 0.3%	3 1.0%	185 62.7%	104 35.3%	4.32	0.582
10	It supports participation in premium markets.	2 0.7%	3 1.0%	36 12.2%	180 61.0%	74 25.1%	4.09	0.684
11	It grants access to tailored financial services.	1 0.3%	10 3.4%	41 13.9%	157 53.2%	86 29.2%	4.07	0.770
12	It enhances support service accessibility.	1 0.3%	4 1.4%	9 3.1%	176 59.7%	105 35.6%	4.29	0.624

13	It broadens marketing reach.	1	2	8	191	93	4.26	0.576
		0.3%	0.7%	2.7%	64.7%	31.5%		
14	It facilitates investment in marketing.	-	4	16	195	80	4.19	0.587
			1.4%	5.4%	66.1%	27.1%		
15	It simplifies cooperative membership.	1	1	17	187	89	4.23	0.594
		0.3%	0.3%	5.8%	63.4%	30.2%		
16	It positions my farm favourably in value chains.	1	4	12	199	79	4.19	0.599
		0.3%	1.4%	4.1%	67.5%	26.8%		
17	It ensures transactional accountability.	1	1	2	162	129	4.41	0.564
		0.3%	0.3%	0.7%	54.9%	43.7%		
18	It eases credit acquisition for market activities.	-	2	13	186	94	4.26	0.568
			0.7%	4.4%	63.1%	31.9%		
19	It allows for effective market monitoring.	2	1	5	174	113	4.34	0.601
		0.7%	0.3%	1.7%	59.0%	38.3%		
20	It gives competitive leverage in markets.	-	2	13	187	93	4.26	0.567
			0.7%	4.4%	63.4%	31.5%		

Weighted Mean =4.27

SD= Strongly Disagree, **D=**Disagree, **U=** Undecided, **A=**Agree and **SA=**Strongly Agree

Table 2 shows the analysis of bank account ownership and its influence on market access among female smallholder farmers. It highlighted a strong consensus on its benefits, with a weighted mean of 4.27. Farmers overwhelmingly agree that having a bank account improves access to agricultural markets (\bar{x} = 4.45), streamlines transactions with buyers (\bar{x} = 4.38), and ensures transactional accountability (\bar{x} = 4.41). Additionally, electronic payments (\bar{x} = 4.43) and strengthened relationships with market players (\bar{x} = 4.32) further illustrated how formal banking enhances financial security and trust in trade. Access to formal finance (\bar{x} = 4.22) and tailored financial services (\bar{x} = 4.07) also indicated that bank accounts facilitated credit acquisition and investment in market growth. However, slightly lower scores on aspects like participation in premium markets (Mean = 4.09) and financial service accessibility (\bar{x} = 4.07) indicated that while banking significantly supports market access, challenges like eligibility for financial products or barriers to premium markets may persist.

Presentation of Hypothesis

Hypothesis: There is no significant effect of financial inclusion practices on the productivity of female smallholder farmers in Ogun State.

Table 3: Regression analysis showing the effect of financial inclusion on the productivity of female smallholder farmers in Ogun State

Variables	F-Ratio	Sig. of P	R	R ²	Adj. R ²	B	T	p-value
Financial inclusion	813.953	<0.001	0.858	0.735	0.734	0.858	28.530	0.001

Source: Fieldwork (2025)

Table 3 showed that the effect of financial inclusion on the productivity of female smallholder farmers in Ogun State was significant. The table also shows a coefficient of multiple correlation of $R = 0.858$ and an R^2 of 0.735. This means that 73.5% of the variance was accounted for by the predictor variable. The significance of the contribution was tested at $p < .05$. The table also showed that the analysis of variance (ANOVA) for the regression yielded an F-ratio of 813.953 (significant at the 0.05 level). This implies that the effect of financial inclusion on the productivity of female smallholder farmers was significant and that other variables not included in this model may have accounted for the remaining variance. The contribution and level of significance of financial inclusion expressed as beta weights ($\beta = .858$, $p(0.001) < .05$) revealed that financial inclusion could independently and significantly predict productivity among female smallholder farmers in the study.

Discussion of Hypothesis

The results from hypothesis one revealed a significant effect of bank account ownership on market access among female smallholder farmers in Ogun State. This study's findings are consistent with the assertion of Chukwulobelu, Enwelum & Obianefo (2024) in the existing literature about financial inclusion and its impact on agricultural market participation research involving rice farmers in Anambra State, Nigeria, showing that access to financial services considerably boosts farmers' ability to engage in agricultural markets. This access improves liquidity and eases the financial challenges they face. Also, it is consistent with study carried out by Arner, Buckley and Zetsche (2020) that emphasize how digital payment systems can reduce transaction costs and enhance the customer experience, which provides smallholder farmers with better financial access. These emphasize the importance of financial inclusion, whether through traditional banking or digital financial tools, in enabling farmers. Bank account ownership facilitates access to formal financial services such as loans, credit, and digital payments, which enable farmers to invest in transportation, storage, and distribution networks, thereby enhancing their ability to reach larger and more profitable markets.

Similarly, the findings in this study agree with study by Gerald, Gama and Augusto (2022), which found that farmers with bank accounts are more likely to engage in structured trade agreements and benefit from government agricultural support programs, improving their overall market participation.

Furthermore, the study highlights that bank account ownership independently predicts market access, emphasizing the role of financial inclusion in improving agricultural commercialization. This study is consistent with the assertion that female smallholder farmers often struggle with limited access to formal financial institutions, which restricts their ability to expand their businesses (Adewale, Lawal, Aberu, & Toriola, 2022). The findings support this claim by showing that farmers with bank accounts can leverage digital banking services and mobile transactions, reducing their dependence on middlemen and enhancing their direct engagement with buyers. This suggests that expanding financial literacy and encouraging female farmers to open and utilize bank accounts could significantly improve their market access and bargaining power.

Additionally, the study demonstrated that bank account ownership not only influences access to markets but also impacts the overall efficiency of market transactions. In line with previous studies carried out by Fowowe (2020), the use of bank accounts enables farmers to receive payments securely, avoid cash-related risks, and establish financial credibility with suppliers and buyers. This, in turn, facilitates trust-based trading relationships and enables female farmers to participate in higher-value agricultural markets. The ability to process digital payments also reduces transaction costs and broadens access to e-commerce and agribusiness platforms, making market participation more convenient and profitable for smallholder farmers.

Given these findings, it is crucial to promote bank account ownership among female smallholder farmers through targeted financial inclusion initiatives. This study also aligns with previous research indicating that banks and microfinance institutions are designing financial products specifically for rural farmers. These products often include features like low-cost account maintenance and mobile banking options (Falola, et al, 2023). This strategy supports broader efforts to improve financial inclusion in rural areas, where access to conventional banking services can be quite limited. By offering adaptable and accessible banking solutions, financial institutions have the potential to connect rural farmers with formal financial systems, eventually promoting greater economic participation and stability. Additionally, government agencies and non-governmental organizations should implement financial education programmes to increase awareness of the benefits of bank account ownership. Since bank account ownership significantly enhances market access, improving financial inclusion for female smallholder farmers in Ogun State will contribute to agricultural development, economic empowerment, and food security in Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

Bank account ownership was a critical factor affecting financial inclusion. The study found that bank account ownership significantly enhanced market access among female smallholder farmers. The R^2 value of 0.605 indicated that bank account ownership accounted for 60.5% of the variance in market access. The beta weight ($\beta = 0.778, p < 0.001$) further supported this finding. The overall effect of financial inclusion on productivity was found to be highly significant. The beta weight ($\beta = 0.858, p < 0.001$) indicated that financial inclusion is a major predictor of productivity among female smallholder farmers.

Further analysis of the relationship between financial inclusion components and productivity revealed several important findings. Access to credit showed a moderate positive correlation with productivity ($r = 0.451$, $p < .001$). Saving practices had a stronger correlation ($r = 0.631$, $p < 0.001$), while bank account ownership ($r = 0.705$, $p < 0.001$) and borrowing practices ($r = 0.714$, $p < 0.001$) demonstrated strong relationships with productivity. These findings indicated that all aspects of financial inclusion contributed to improved productivity levels among female smallholder farmers.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study explored the level of financial inclusion among female smallholder farmers in Ogun State, Nigeria, and its impact on their agricultural productivity, income generation, and market access. Through quantitative analysis, several key findings emerged regarding financial access, saving behaviors, credit, and borrowing practices, and their direct correlation with productivity and income outcomes for female farmers. The study demonstrated that financial inclusion plays a crucial role in enhancing the productivity and economic well-being of female smallholder farmers in Ogun State. However, significant challenges persist, particularly in accessing formal financial services, credit facilities, and tailored financial products that meet the specific needs of female farmers. A substantial proportion of the farmers reported difficulties in securing financial services and credit, which has hindered their ability to invest in quality farm inputs and expand their agricultural activities. Despite these limitations, a strong culture of savings and financial empowerment was observed among the farmers, indicating that with better financial access, they could achieve greater economic stability and productivity.

The findings also highlighted the significant impact of financial inclusion variables such as access to credit, savings practices, bank account ownership, and borrowing practices on the productivity and income generation of female smallholder farmers. Statistical analyses confirmed that these factors collectively accounted for a substantial variance in productivity, with borrowing practices and bank account ownership having the strongest influence. Furthermore, access to credit was found to be a critical determinant of crop yield, while saving practices significantly contributed to income generation.

Based on the findings of this study offers the following recommendations:

1. **Encouraging Savings and Bank Account Ownership:** Since savings practices were found to significantly impact income generation, financial institutions should promote savings schemes tailored to the needs of female smallholder farmers. Rural banks and microfinance institutions should offer incentives such as higher interest rates on agricultural savings accounts, matching savings programs, and mobile savings platforms. Additionally, efforts should be made to increase bank account ownership among female farmers by simplifying account opening procedures, reducing transaction costs, and expanding banking infrastructure in rural areas.
2. **Strengthening Digital Financial Services and Mobile Banking:** To bridge the financial access gap, digital financial services should be expanded in rural areas. Mobile banking, mobile money services, and fintech solutions should be promoted as convenient and accessible financial tools for female smallholder farmers. Telecommunication companies

and financial service providers should collaborate to offer affordable mobile financial solutions that enable farmers to save, borrow, and transact without needing to visit physical bank branches.

3. Expanding Financial Literacy and Education Programmes: To maximize the benefits of financial inclusion, female farmers should be provided with financial literacy training on topics such as credit management, savings, investment, and financial planning. Government agencies, NGOs, and financial institutions should collaborate to organize workshops and training programs that equip female farmers with the necessary knowledge and skills to make informed financial decisions. Training on digital financial services, including mobile banking and online transactions, should also be incorporated to help farmers adopt modern financial tools.

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